

Supplementary Information

Propane dehydrogenation over Pt and Ga-containing MFI zeolites with modified acidity and textural properties

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Figure S1. Argon (87K) adsorption-desorption isotherms for (a) Pt-containing n-ZSM-5 catalysts and (c) Ga-containing catalysts.

Figure S2. FTIR spectra in the region of pyridine vibrations for (a) the Pt-containing catalysts and (b) Ga-containing catalysts.

Figure S3. Concentration of Brønsted and Lewis acid sites as a function of the pyridine desorption temperature: (a-b) Pt-containing n-ZSM-5 catalysts and (c-d) Ga-containing catalysts.

Figure S4. EDS elemental mapping of (a-d) metal oxides-containing catalysts and (e-h) Ga-containing catalysts.